

***In vitro* anti-inflammatory activity of a new triterpenoid saponin from the stems of *Glirisia sepium* Jacq.**

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Abstract : A new triterpenoid saponin (**1**) has been isolated from the methanolic extract of the stems of the *Glirisia sepium* Jacq. along with a known compound 3-*O*-[α -L-arabinopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- α -L-arabinopyranosyl]-28-*O*-[β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-{ β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 6)}- β -D-glucopyranosyl]-29-hydroxyhederagenin (**2**). A new compound **1** has m.p. 272–274 °C, m.f. C₄₆H₇₄O₁₇, [M]⁺ *m/z* 898 was characterized as 3-*O*-[β -D-xylopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)]- α -L-arabinopyranosyl echinocystic acid 28-*O*- β -D-galactopyranosyl ester by various colour reactions, chemical degradations and spectral analysis. *In vitro* anti-inflammatory activity of compound **1** showed significant effect against human red blood cell (HRBC) membrane stabilization.

Keywords : *Glirisia sepium* Jacq., Fabaceae, stems, triterpenoid saponin, bidesmosidic, anti-inflammatory activity.

Introduction

*Glirisia sepium*¹ belongs to family Fabaceae, which is commonly known as 'Mata Ratón or Ggiripushpa'. It is medium sized tree which grows about 3–6 m high, bark smooth greenish-brown, lenticellate. Its leaves are 15–30 cm long. Its flowers are pale rosy-pink to white in colour. Pods compressed, glabrous, pendent, linear; seeds flat, elliptic and yellow. This plant is used as insecticidal, nematicidal and antibacterial². The leaf extracts is used as antioxidant³. It is also used in urticarial and rash. Earlier workers^{4–9} have reported various active constituents from this plant. This paper deals with the isolation and structural elucidation of a new triterpenoid saponin (**1**), 3-*O*-[β -D-xylopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)]- α -L-arabinopyranosyl echinocystic acid 28-*O*- β -D-galactopyranosyl ester along with a known compound 3-*O*-[α -L-arabinopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- α -L-arabinopyranosyl]-28-*O*-[α -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-{ β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 6)}- β -D-glucopyranosyl]-29-hydroxyhederagenin from the methanolic extract of the stems of the plant.

Results and discussion

The methanolic extract of the stems of the plant yielded

a new compound **1**, m.p. 272–274 °C, m.f. C₄₆H₇₄O₁₇, [M]⁺ *m/z* 898 (FABMS). It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test for triterpenoid saponin¹⁰. In the IR spectrum, two peaks at 3445, 1661 cm⁻¹ were assigned for hydroxyl group and double bond respectively. In ¹H NMR spectrum (300 MHz, CD₃OD) signals at δ 1.09, 0.89, 0.98, 0.91, 1.36, 0.91, 1.11 (each 3H, s, Me \times 7) showed the presence of seven singlet of methyl of an olean-12-ene-type triterpene. The signal at δ 5.31 (1H, *t*, *J* 3.5 Hz, H-12) showed the presence of trisubstituted olefinic proton. A double doublet at δ 3.15 (1H, dd, *J* 12.0, 4.5 Hz, H-3) was assigned to H-3 and 4.62 (1H, br s) for H-16. The anomeric proton signal at δ 4.73 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, H-1'), 4.98 (1H, d, *J* 6.7 Hz, H-1''), 5.33 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, H-1'''), were assigned to H-1', H-1'', H-1''' of D-xylose, L-arabinose and D-galactose respectively. In ¹³C NMR spectrum (75 MHz, CD₃OD), two signals at δ 122.91 (C-12), 144.52 (C-13), showed the presence of double bond between C-12 and C-13. In ¹³C NMR spectrum a downfield signal at δ 176.32 showed the presence of carboxylic group at C-28. Two signal at δ 90.02 (C-3) and 73.83 (C-16) revealed the presence of hydroxyl group at C-3 and C-16. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound **1** exhibited 46 signals, out of them 30 signals could be as-

signed to the aglycone and 16 signals to the sugar moieties, suggesting the nature of compound **1** as bidesmosidic.

In the mass spectrum of the compound **1**, characteristic ion peak at $[M^+]$ m/z 898, 766, 634 and 472 were found by subsequent losses from the molecular ion of each molecular of D-xylose, L-arabinose and D-galactose showing D-xylose as terminal sugar, L-arabinose was linked at C-3 position of aglycone.

Acid hydrolysis of compound **1** with ethanol and 10% H_2SO_4 gave compound **1a**. It has m.p. 231–233 °C, molecular formula $C_{30}H_{48}O_4$ $[M]^+$ m/z 472 (FABMS). It responded to all the colour reactions of triterpenoid¹¹. It was identified as echinocystic acid. The aqueous hydrolysate obtained after acid hydrolysis of the compound **1** was neutralized with $BaCO_3$ and the $BaSO_4$ was filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and subjected to paper chromatography examination using *n*-BAW (4 : 1 : 5) as solvent and aniline hydrogen phthalate as detecting agent yielding D-xylose (R_f 0.28), L-arabinose (R_f 0.21) and D-galactose (R_f 0.16) by (Co-Pc and Co-TLC)¹².

Permethylation¹³ of compound **1** yielded methylated aglycone identified as 16 α -methoxy echinocystic acid confirming that glycosidation was involved at C-3 and C-28, methylated sugars were identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-xylose (RG 0.94), 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-L-arabinose

(RG 0.64) and 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose (RG 0.88) suggesting that C-1'' of D-xylose was attached with C-4' of L-arabinose and C-1' of L-arabinose attached to C-3 position of aglycone and C-1''' of D-galactose attached to carboxylic group at C-28 position of aglycone thus the interlinkage (1→4) was found between D-xylose and L-arabinose and L-arabinose directly attached to C-3 position of aglycone. This linkage and the linkage between D-galactose attached to carboxylic group at C-28 position of aglycone was further confirmed by ¹³C NMR spectral data. Periodate oxidation¹⁴ of compound **1** confirmed that three sugars were present in pyranose form.

Enzymatic hydrolysis¹⁵ of compound **1** with enzyme almond emulsin liberated D-galactose (R_f 0.16) first, followed by D-xylose (R_f 0.28) and proaglycone identified as α -L-arabinopyranosyl echinocystic acid suggesting the presence of β -linkage between D-galactose, D-xylose and proaglycone. Proaglycone was hydrolysed with enzyme takadiastase liberated L-arabinose (R_f 0.21) and aglycone confirming the presence of α -linkage between L-arabinose and aglycone.

Quantitative examination¹⁶ of the sugars present in the hydrolysate revealed that the three sugars were present in equimolecular proportions indicating that the triterpenoid saponin consists of one molecule of each,

Fig. 1. Compound 1.

aglycone (sapogenin), D-xylose, L-arabinose and D-galactose.

In vitro anti-inflammatory activity of compound **1** has been carried out by Human Red Blood Cell membrane stabilization method. The percentage of membrane stabilisation for compound **1** and Diclofenac sodium were carried out at different concentrations (100, 250, 500, 1000 µg/ml). From Table 1 it was concluded that compound **1** showed positive response as compared to Diclofenac sodium and also observe that when the concentration is increased then membrane stabilization is increased and membrane hemolysis is decreased. Hence compound **1** showed good anti-inflammatory activity.

Experimental

General experimental procedure :

All the melting points were determined on a thermo electrical melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were measured on Shimadzu 84005 FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr matrix. UV spectra were recorded on Systronics-2201 UV/Vis Double Beam spectrophotometer in MeOH. The NMR spectral data were recorded at 300 MHz for ¹H NMR and 75 MHz for ¹³C NMR on Bruker DRX 300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and CD₃OD as solvent. The FABMS were recorded on a Joel SX (102) Mass spectrometer.

Plant material :

The stems of the plant were collected locally around Sagar region and were taxonomically authenticated by Taxonomist, Department of Botany, Dr. H. S. Gour Central University, Sagar (Madhya Pradesh), India. A voucher specimen (Bot/Her/A/3247) has been deposited in the Natural Products Laboratory, Department of Chemistry of this university.

Extraction and isolation :

Air-dried and powdered stems (4 kg) of the plant were extracted with 95% ethanol (60–80 °C) in Soxhlet apparatus for 74 h. The total ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and successively partitioned with petroleum ether (40–60%), CHCl₃, CH₃COOC₂H₅, CH₃COCH₃ and CH₃OH. The methanol soluble fraction of the plant was concentrated under reduced pressure by rotary vacuum evaporator to give brown viscous mass. It gave two spots on TLC examination using chloroform : methanol : water (6 : 4 : 2) as solvent and I₂ vapours as visualizing agent indicating it to be mixture of two compounds **1** and **2**. These were separated by column chromatography over silica gel column using CHCl₃ : MeOH (3 : 6) as eluent and studied separately.

Study of compound **1** :

It was crystallized from methanol to give light brown crystalline compound (1.75 g), m.p. 272–274 °C, m.f. C₄₆H₇₄O₁₇ [M]⁺ *m/z* 898 (FABMS). Found (%) : C, 60.62; H, 8.13; O, 30.93. Calcd. for m.f. C₄₆H₇₄O₁₇ : C, 61.46; H, 8.24; O, 30.28%; IR (KBr) : 3445, 2941, 1661, 1454, 1038, 1353, 1124, 850, 580 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CD₃OD) : δ 1.09 (3H, s, Me-23), 0.89 (3H, s, Me-24), 0.98 (3H, s, Me-25), 0.91 (3H, s, Me-26), 1.36 (3H, s, Me-27), 0.91 (3H, s, Me-29), 1.11 (3H, s, Me-30), 1.09 (1H, m, H-1_a), 1.62 (1H, m, H-1_b), 1.79 (1H, m, H-2_a), 1.92 (1H, m, H-2_b), 3.15 (1H, dd, *J* 12.0, 4.5 Hz, H-3), 0.68 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz, H-5), 1.55 (1H, m, H-6_a), 1.39 (1H, m, H-6_b), 1.61 (1H, m, H-7_a), 1.36 (1H, m, H-7_b), 1.69 (1H, m, H-9), 1.95 (2H, m, H-11), 5.31 (1H, *t*, *J* 3.5 Hz, H-12), 1.82 (1H, m, H-15_a), 1.38 (1H, m, H-15_b), 4.62 (1H, br s, H-16), 3.05 (1H, dd, *J* 14.0, 3.5 Hz, H-18), 2.34 (1H, m, H-19_a), 1.00 (1H, m, H-19_b), 1.92 (1H, m, H-21_a), 1.15 (1H, m, H-

Table 1. Effect of compound **1** and Diclofenac sodium (drug) on HRBC membrane hemolysis and membrane stabilization

Concentration of Diclofenac sodium and compound 1 in reaction mixture (µg/ml)	% Membrane stabilization of drug	% Hemolysis of drug	% Membrane stabilization of compound 1	% Hemolysis of compound 1
100	43.53519	56.46481	43.69885	56.30115
250	61.70213	38.29787	65.30278	34.69722
500	79.86907	20.13093	81.66939	18.33061
1000	91.65303	8.346972	93.28969	6.710311

21_b), 1.89 (1H, m, H-22_a), 1.78 (1H, m, H-22_b), 2.83 (1H, d, *J* 11.2 Hz, H-28), 4.73 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, H-1'), 3.69 (1H, dd, *J* 8.1, 6.5 Hz, H-2'), 3.77 (1H, dd, *J* 8.2, 3.1 Hz, H-3'), 3.83 (1H, m, H-4'), 3.89 (1H, m, H-5_a'), 3.47 (1H, m, H-5_b'), 4.98 (1H, d, *J* 6.7 Hz, H-1''), 3.73 (1H, dd, *J* 7.5, 8.5 Hz, H-2''), 3.36 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, H-3''), 3.43 (1H, s, H-4''), 3.69 (2H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz, H-5''), 5.33 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz, H-1'''), 4.12 (1H, dd, *J* 7.3, 9.5 Hz, H-2'''), 3.57 (1H, dd, *J* 7.2, 3.5 Hz, H-3'''), 4.18 (1H, dd, *J* 3.2, 1.5 Hz, H-4'''), 3.51 (1H, ddd, *J* 1.5, 5.5, 7.5 Hz, H-5'''), 3.73 (1H, dd, *J* 11.2, 6.3 Hz, H-6_a'''), 4.42 (1H, dd, *J* 11.4, 5.2 Hz, H-6_b'''); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CD₃OD) : δ 39.87 (C-1), 31.91 (C-2), 90.02 (C-3), 42.12 (C-4), 56.82 (C-5), 19.52 (C-6), 35.71 (C-7), 40.21 (C-8), 48.63 (C-9), 38.12 (C-10), 24.93 (C-11), 122.91 (C-12), 144.52 (C-13), 40.92 (C-14), 30.81 (C-15), 73.83 (C-16), 51.23 (C-17), 41.42 (C-18), 47.82 (C-19), 32.03 (C-20), 36.14 (C-21), 33.12 (C-22), 26.23 (C-23), 18.12 (C-24), 17.28 (C-25), 18.81 (C-26), 25.29 (C-27), 176.32 (C-28), 32.25 (C-29), 26.72 (C-30), 103.8 (C-1'), 70.8 (C-2'), 75.4 (C-3'), 68.8 (C-4'), 67.7 (C-5'), 104.3 (C-1''), 75.1 (C-2''), 83.4 (C-3''), 69.4 (C-4''), 68.2 (C-5''), 104.5 (C-1'''), 71.9 (C-2'''), 83.9 (C-3'''), 70.5 (C-4'''), 75.78 (C-5'''), 64.13 (C-6''', CH₃).

Study of compound 2 :

It was crystallized from methanol to give colourless crystalline compound (0.710 g), m.p. 253–255 °C, m.f. C₆₄H₁₀₄O₃₂ [M]⁺ *m/z* 1384 (FABMS). Found (%): C, 55.42; H, 8.12; O, 35.97. Calcd. for C₆₄H₁₀₄O₃₂: C, 55.49; H, 7.51; O, 36.99; IR (KBr): 3150, 2946, 2881, 1730, 1689, 1453, 1370, 1225, 1012, 739 cm⁻¹. It was identified as 3-*O*-[α-L-arabinopyranosyl-(1→3)-α-L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1→2)-α-L-arabinopyranosyl]-28-*O*-[β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→2)-{β-D-glucopyranosyl-(1→6)}-β-D-glucopyranosyl]-29-hydroxyhederagenin by comparison of its spectral data with reported literature values¹⁷.

Acid hydrolysis of compound 1 :

Compound 1 (450 mg) was dissolved in ethanol (25 mL) and refluxed with 10% H₂SO₄ (20 mL) on water bath for 7 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated and allowed to cool and residue was extracted with diethyl ether. The ether layer was washed with water and evaporated to dryness. The residue was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel column using CHCl₃ :

MeOH (5 : 10) as solvent to yield compound 1a as aglycone, which was identified as echinocystic acid. The aqueous hydrolysate was neutralized with BaCO₃ and the BaSO₄ was filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography examination using *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water [*n*-BAW, 4 : 1 : 5] as solvent and aniline hydrogen phthalate as spraying reagent which showed the presence of D-xylose (*R_f* 0.28), L-arabinose (*R_f* 0.21) and D-galactose (*R_f* 0.16) by (Co-Pc and Co-TLC).

Study of compound 1a :

It has m.p. 231–233 °C, molecular formula C₃₀H₄₈O₄ [M]⁺ *m/z* 472 (FABMS). Found : C, 76.22; H, 10.21; O, 13.49. Calcd. for m.f. C₃₀H₄₈O₄ : C, 76.27; H, 10.16; O, 13.55; IR (KBr) : 3534, 3400, 1664, 1447, 1100 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CD₃OD) : δ 1.09 (3H, s, Me-23), 0.89 (3H, s, Me-24), 0.98 (3H, s, Me-25), 0.91 (3H, s, Me-26), 1.36 (3H, s, Me-27), 0.91 (3H, s, Me-29), 1.11 (3H, s, Me-30), 1.09 (1H, m, H-1_a), 1.62 (1H, m, H-1_b), 1.79 (1H, m, H-2_a), 1.92 (1H, m, H-2_b), 3.15 (1H, dd, *J* 12.0, 4.5 Hz, H-3), 0.68 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz, H-5), 1.55 (1H, m, H-6_a), 1.39 (1H, m, H-6_b), 1.61 (1H, m, H-7_a), 1.36 (1H, m, H-7_b), 1.69 (1H, m, H-9), 1.95 (2H, m, H-11), 5.31 (1H, *t*, *J* 3.5 Hz, H-12), 1.82 (1H, m, H-15_a), 1.38 (1H, m, H-15_b), 4.62 (1H, br s, H-16), 3.05 (1H, dd, *J* 14.0, 3.5 Hz, H-18), 2.34 (1H, m, H-19_a), 1.00 (1H, m, H-19_b), 1.92 (1H, m, H-21_a), 1.15 (1H, m, H-21_b), 1.89 (1H, m, H-22_a), 1.78 (1H, m, H-22_b), 2.83 (1H, d, *J* 11.2 Hz, H-28); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CD₃OD) : δ 39.87 (C-1), 31.91 (C-2), 90.02 (C-3), 42.12 (C-4), 56.82 (C-5), 19.52 (C-6), 35.71 (C-7), 40.21 (C-8), 48.63 (C-9), 38.12 (C-10), 24.93 (C-11), 122.91 (C-12), 144.52 (C-13), 40.92 (C-14), 30.81 (C-15), 73.83 (C-16), 51.23 (C-17), 41.42 (C-18), 47.82 (C-19), 32.03 (C-20), 36.14 (C-21), 33.12 (C-22), 26.23 (C-23), 18.12 (C-24), 17.28 (C-25), 18.81 (C-26), 25.29 (C-27), 176.32 (C-28), 32.25 (C-29), 26.72 (C-30).

Permethylation of compound 1 :

Compound 1 (35 mg) was dissolved in DMF (25 mL) and treated with MeI (5 mL) and Ag₂O (15 mg) in 150 mL round bottomed flask fitted with condenser and refluxed for two days. The reaction mixture was filtered and washed with DMF. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and treated with CHCl₃ (25 mL) and washed

with water. After removal of solvent a syrupy mass was found which was hydrolysed with 7% H₂SO₄ (5 mL) to give aglycone, identified as 16 α -methoxy echinocystic acid. The aqueous hydrolysate obtained after the removal of aglycone was neutralized with BaCO₃ and the BaSO₄ was filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and subjected to paper chromatography examination on Whatmann filter paper No.1 using *n*-butanol : ethanol : water (5 : 1 : 4) as solvent system and aniline hydrogen phthalate as spraying agent. The methylated sugars were identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-xylose (RG 0.94), 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-L-arabinose (RG 0.64) and 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose (RG 0.88).

Enzymatic hydrolysis of compound 1 :

Compound **1** (30 mg) was dissolved in MeOH (20 mL) and hydrolyzed with equal volume of enzyme almond emulsin. The reaction mixture was allowed to stay at room temperature for two days and filtered. The hydrolysate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography examination using *n*-BAW (4 : 1 : 5) as solvent system and aniline hydrogen phthalate as a spraying reagent which showed the presence of D-galactose and D-xylose suggesting the presence of β linkage between D-galactose (R_f 0.16) and proaglycone as well as between D-xylose (R_f 0.28) and proaglycone. Proaglycone on further hydrolysis with enzyme takadiastase yielded L-arabinose (R_f 0.21) and aglycone suggesting the presence of a linkage between L-arabinose and aglycone.

Evaluation of in vitro anti-inflammatory activity of compound 1 :

In vitro anti-inflammatory activity of compound **1** has been carried out by Human Red Blood Cell membrane stabilization method^{18,19}. Blood was collected from healthy volunteers and it was mixed with equal volume of sterilized Alsevers solution (2% dextrose, 0.8% sodium citrate, 0.5% citric acid and 0.42% NaCl). This blood solution was centrifuged at 3000 rpm and the packed cells were separated. The packed cells were washed with isosaline solution and 10% v/v suspension was made with isosaline. This HRBC suspension was used for the estimation of anti-inflammatory activity. 1.0 ml of different concentrations of compound **1** and reference drug (Diclofenac sodium) were separately mixed with 1 mL of

phosphate buffer, 2 mL of hyposaline and 0.5 mL of HRBC suspension control solution was prepared by 1 mL of phosphate buffer, 2 mL of distilled water and 0.5 mL of HRBC suspension. All the reaction mixtures were incubated at 35 °C for 25 min and centrifuged at 3000 rpm. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the hemoglobin content was estimated by UV/Vis Double Beam spectrophotometer at 560 nm. The absorbance of control was measured at 0.611.

The percentage of hemolysis and membrane stabilisation were calculated by following formulae :

$$\% \text{ Hemolysis} =$$

$$(\text{Optical density of test sample} / \text{Optical density of control}) \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ Membrane stabilisation} = [1 - (\text{OD sample} / \text{OD control})] \times 100\%$$

The results obtained from experimental findings are recorded in the Table 1.

Conclusion

Thus on the basis of above evidences the structure of compound **1** was established as 3-*O*-[β -D-xylopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)]- α -L-arabinopyranosyl echinocystic acid 28-*O*- β -D-galactopyranosyl ester, along with a known compound 3-*O*-[α -L-arabinopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 3)]- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- α -L-arabinopyranosyl]-28-*O*-[β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)]- β -D-glucopyranosyl]-29-hydroxyhederagenin from the methanolic extract of the stems of the plant. Compound **1** showed significant *in vitro* anti-inflammatory activity against Human Red Blood Cell (HRBC) membrane stabilization. Hence, compound **1** can be used as a potent anti-inflammatory agent.

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